

Journal title

Building Information Modelling (BIM) and construction project management

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Abstract

Building Information Modelling (BIM) is turning into a thorough shared interaction in the construction industry. Despite its short history, BIM has had an expanding development during the last decade. This is going on fundamentally because of its abilities on construction projects. BIM can make a typical language between all gatherings and framework divisions in an undertaking and make them an incorporated group. The methodology of BIM emphatically coordinates with incorporated task conveyance frameworks. The job of BIM as an organizer of venture framework is very like the obligations of a task manager. BIM incorporates various controls by successful correspondence, examines the task frameworks for constructability, gauges the expense and season of projects whenever utilizing amount departures, draws a higher perspective of projects utilizing representation and assembles cooperative groups. Every one of these are what a venture manager does in an alternate scale during an undertaking life cycle.

This paper presents definitions and qualities of Building Information Modelling (BIM), and analyzes its effects for the lifecycle management of construction project with a run of the typical case. Based on BIM, the paper likewise talks about the new prerequisites of the capacities and characteristics of the project managers.

Keywords: Building information model (BIM); BIM for lifecycle evaluation ; Specialized Parts of BIM; Project management; Project management approaches; Role of BIM in Project Management; Effects of BIM on Project Management;

1. Introduction

Due to several distinct businesses working on busy sites, construction projects are becoming more challenging. Time-consuming preparation, unnecessary movements, and material management etc, are the most important factor of projects failure. The most important responsibility of a project manager is to boost productivity, efficiency, infrastructure value, excellence, and the project's ability to survive, and reduce lifecycle expenses and times consumed through increasing cooperation and relation of stakeholders of a project. But at present, Building Information Modelling (BIM) has been able to make these complex jobs much easier. BIM helps the construction

manager to gather data and information from the relevant disciplines and communicate them more effectively.

1.1. Building Information Modeling (BIM)

Building Information Modeling (BIM) can be defined as a reliable, digital, three dimensional, virtual representation of the project to be built for use in design decision-making, construction scheduling and planning, cost estimates and maintenance of construction projects (Words & Images, 2009). The BIM Handbook (2008) defined BIM as a computer-aided modeling technology for the purpose of managing the information of a construction project focusing on production, communication and analysis of building information models. The National Building Information Model Standard Project Committee defined the BIM as following:

“A BIM is a digital representation of physical and functional characteristics of a facility. As such it serves as a shared knowledge resource for information about a facility forming a reliable basis for decisions during its lifecycle from inception onward.”

The concept of BIM theoretically emerged and was developed at Georgia Institute of Technology in the late 1970s and grew quickly after that. The development happened due to the expanding consideration paid to development groups and firms that discovered benefits in utilizing BIM to incorporate the cycle of the development projects and overseeing them. The term Building Information Modeling was first used in 2002 to describe virtual design, construction and facilities management (Harris, 2010). In 1986, Graphisoft released its new program as a virtual-building solution. This software, Archicad, was a significant advancement above previous CAD applications at the time, as it allowed for the construction of three-dimensional (3D) models of projects (Dey, 2010). When Autodesk launched "Building Information Modeling" (Autodesk, 2003), the terms Building Information Modeling and Building Information Model, as well as the acronym BIM, were generally used.

1.2. Construction project management (CPM)

Construction project management is run by a construction project manager. This person is tasked with the planning, coordination, budgeting and supervision of the construction project. Project management is the process of managing a team's efforts to meet all project objectives while staying within budget restrictions. Typically, this data is described in project documentation, which is prepared at the start of the development process. Scope, time, and budget are the three main restraints. The second difficulty is to optimize the allocation of required inputs and apply them to achieve predetermined goals. The goal of project management is to generate a finished product that meets the client's requirements. In many circumstances, project management's goal is to mold or reform the client's brief in order to effectively fulfill the client's goals. Once the client's goals are defined, they should guide all decisions made by others participating in the project, such as project managers, designers, contractors, and subcontractors. Decision-making is hampered by ill-defined or overly strict project management objectives. A project is a short-term undertaking having a clear beginning and end (generally time-limited, and often constrained by funding or staffing) that is undertaken to achieve certain goals and objectives, usually to bring about beneficial change or additional value. Projects differ from business as usual (or operations) in that they are repeatable, permanent, or semi-permanent functional activities that create products or services. In practice, managing such disparate

production methods necessitates the development of disparate technical skills and managerial tactics.

Construction project manager responsible for the following tasks: Estimate and negotiate project costs. Construction projects comprise the fundamental piece of all orders projects because of their amount, variety and cost. According to the US Census Bureau News (2013), the construction industry spent more than \$874 billion in 2013. These projects range in size from tiny residential or retail developments to large multipurpose developments. Needless to say, with any scale of a construction project, there is a necessity for managing it. The management of construction projects requires knowledge of modern management as well as an understanding of all construction processes. Along with the change in technology, organizational arrangement or procedures and new features and methods, the management of construction projects differs (Hendrickson, 2000). Construction project management is a series of activities for determining how, when and by whom the work, including all life cycle activities, will be performed.

Similar to the Project Management Body of Knowledge (PMBOK) definitions, the construction project manager handles project management planning, cost management, time management, quality management, contract administration, safety management and risk management. The project manager is also in charge of communication between all stakeholders on the project including owner, designers, engineers, professional crew and administrative staffs. Generally, construction project management shares the common and overall characteristics of general projects, therefore, the rules and methods required for general project management can be applied to this type of projects.

2. BIM FOR LIFECYCLE EVALUATION

While there are not many definitions accessible for BIM in the literature, the creators propose a more The authors provide a more comprehensive definition in order to provide the reader with a clear knowledge on behind the real agenda BIM. As a result, this concept encourages consideration of the natural environment, user environment, and owner satisfaction throughout the lifecycle.

“BIM is defined as the use of the ICT technologies to streamline the building lifecycle processes to provide a safer and more productive environment for its occupants, and to assert the least possible environmental impact from its existence, and to be more operationally efficient for its owners throughout the building lifecycle;

In the most basic form, BIM is the use of a database system to encapsulate built facilities with specific stakeholder perspectives. It is a methodology to integrate digital descriptions of all the building objects and their relationships to others in a precise manner, so that stakeholders can query, simulate and estimate activities and their effects of the building process as a lifecycle entity. Therefore, BIM can provide the required valued judgments that create more sustainable infrastructures, which satisfy their owners and occupants. However, while users and owners can change during the period of a building's lifecycle at various intervals, the most important component is to minimize the influence on the natural environment. While this can be accomplished in a variety of ways using mature BIM integrated construction approaches, we won't go through them here because we're primarily interested in construction lifecycle management.

3. DIGITAL CONSTRUCTION THROUGH BIM SYSTEMS

The term 'digital construction' is being utilized by the Danish Government since mid 2007 which depended on a political drive (http://www.deaca.dk/Digital_Construction) to address low usefulness in the construction area. As referenced, it tries to coordinate cycles all through the whole lifecycle with the concentration to make and reuse predictable digital data. Until this point, there are numerous undertakings that have used BIM frameworks inside; natural arranging, plan and advancement, enhancement, security and code checking, construction, and have understood its advantages. Such activities have prescribed BIM frameworks as a solution for address low usefulness issues. In other words, this situation is pressuring the construction industry to go through a paradigm shift to (i) increase; productivity, efficiency, infrastructure value, quality and sustainability, (ii) reduce; lifecycle costs, lead times and duplications, via effective collaboration and communication of stakeholders in construction projects.

4. PRIMARY TECHNICAL PARTS OF BIM

BIM includes a variety of features that can be useful in project management. These increasingly developed features can be summarized as follows: (Lahdou & Zetterman, 2011)

- **Construct ability**

Using BIM, it would be possible for teammates in a project to review and handle constructability issues and (if needed) promote issues into RFIs. In addition, visual information can be provided from a vantage point to show the problems. This visual information accompanying markup allows further investigation for finding solutions and, thus, mitigates the risks.

- **Clash Detection**

One of the common problems of different disciplines' plans for a construction project is the geometrical design inconsistencies. This issue happens when there is an overlap between the plans of different disciplines. Using BIM, it would be possible to bring the plans together and detect the clashes. Modifying the aesthetic problems is another possibility of this visual checking.

- **Analysis**

Helping the project managers, designers and engineers in doing more analyses and enabling better decision making is another aspect of BIM. By linking the building information models to appropriate tools, it would be possible to analyze the energy consumption of a construction project and then find better solutions such as changing materials and orientation, mass and space, etc. Moreover, light, mechanical and acoustics analyses are also available to be performed by BIM.

- **Time & Cost Estimation (4D & 5D)**

Time and cost estimation are other features of BIM which enable project managers to visualize the construction project at any point in time and have a clear understanding of project phases. Time and cost estimation, which are generally called 4D and 5D, can be properly utilized in the first stages of a project and facilitate the decision making process with minimum cost and time needed. Furthermore, BIM has the capability to simulate the various alternatives for a construction project and hence helps project managers and executives to reliably predict the consequences of their decisions.

- **Integration**

The project team can deal and interact with a unified model when a composite model is built from an amalgam of various disciplines' models. Having this capability, and through the different phases of a construction project, BIM can coordinate the design, analysis, and construction activities on a project and, therefore, results in integrity of projects.

- Quantity Take-off

Quantity takeoffs in a BIM model can be very helpful for the project teams and managers to analyze their decision and have a clear and reliable insight to various alternatives in the design phase or even throughout the project lifecycle. Since there is a possibility of integration between the BIM model and a database containing cost estimation, an accurate estimation can be obtained faster. Moreover, these takeoff items can be used easily in procurement procedure.

- Element Based Models

Since the BIM models generally are composed of objects –and not geometries, such as line, surface, etc. – the whole model can be divided into a specific number of smaller objects. This breakdown makes it possible to have a defined and clear scope of projects. The distinction between the elements will result in a better management design, estimation and construction.

- Collaboration and Team Building

Collaboration and team building is another key factor for BIM success on construction projects. All efforts made by various specialties on a project are unified and applied to one model. This results in direct correspondence and team building. All disciplines have to work on a unified model as a team and have an effective collaboration during a project using the BIM concept.

- Communication

The Nature of a unified model to input, modify and analyze the data in BIM models will improve communication and collaboration between all parties involved on the construction project including project managers, architects, engineers, and contractors. These unique building models facilitate the communication throughout the project and lessen the disputes between different parties.

5. PRIMARY PROJECT MANAGEMENT TYPES

Any project can benefit from project management techniques. It is frequently adjusted to a certain sort of project based on the size, nature, industry, or sector of the project. For example, the construction industry, which concentrates on the delivery of items such as buildings, roads, and bridges, has evolved its own specialized type of project management known as construction project management, in which project managers can be trained and qualified. IT project management, which specializes in the delivery of technical assets and services that must pass through multiple lifecycle phases such as planning, design, development, testing, and deployment, has grown within the information technology sector. The complexities of biotechnology research and development are the focus of biotechnology project management. Despite the fact that many people consider localization project management to be a completely distinct subject, it includes the application of many typical project management principles to translation projects. There is public project management, which encompasses all government-funded public works that can be completed by government agencies or outsourced out to contractors. Another way to categorize project management is according to whether it is hard (physical) or soft (non-physical). All project management types have three essential aims in common:

time, quality, and money. In order for projects to be judged a success or failure, they must be finished on time, within budget, and according to previously established quality standards, i.e. they must fulfill the Iron Triangle or Triple Constraint. Project managers create and use repeating templates that are relevant to the industry they're working in for each sort of project management. This permits project plans to become more detailed and reproducible, with the goal of improving quality, lowering delivery costs, and shortening the time it takes to produce project results.

6. PROJECT MANAGEMENT APPROACHES

According to a 2017 research, the success of every project is determined by how effectively four essential components are matched with the project's contextual dynamics, which are referred to as the four P's.

- Plan: The activities of planning and forecasting.
- Process: The overall approach to all activities and project governance.
- People: Including dynamics of how they collaborate and communicate.
- Power: Lines of authority, decision-makers, organograms, policies for implementation and the like.

6.1. Benefits realization management

Benefits realization management (BRM) improves on traditional project management approaches by focusing on project outcomes (benefits) rather than goods or outputs, and then assessing the extent to which this occurs to keep a project on track. This can assist to decrease the chance of a finished project becoming a failure by meeting agreed-upon requirements (outputs), i.e. project success, but failing to meet the benefits (outcomes), i.e. product success. Also, BRM methods seek to guarantee the strategic alignment of project outputs with company goals. Recent study demonstrates that BRM techniques influence project performance from a strategic viewpoint across different countries and industries, lending credence to their efficacy. The strategic impact refers to these broader implications. Accepting to produce a computer system that would process staff data and manage payroll, holidays, and staff personnel records in less time with fewer mistakes is an example of delivering a project to requirements. The agreement under BRM might be to accomplish a certain decrease in the number of staff hours and mistakes necessary to process and manage staff data after the system is installed, as compared to before the system was installed.

6.2. Critical chain project management (CCPM)

Critical chain project management (CCPM) is a method of planning and managing projects that emphasizes the resources (people, equipment, physical space) required to execute project tasks. It was developed by Eliyahu M. Goldratt. It differs from more traditional methods that derive from critical path and PERT algorithms, which emphasize task order and rigid scheduling. A critical chain project network strives to keep resources levelled, and requires that they be flexible in start times. (CCPM) is an application of the theory of constraints (TOC) to project planning and management. It is designed to deal with the uncertainties inherent in project management while

taking into account the limited availability of resources (physical, human skills, as well as management and support capacity) required to complete projects. The goal is to increase the number of projects that pass through a company (throughput). The system limitation for all projects, as well as the resources, are recognized utilizing the first three of TOC's five concentrating phases. To take advantage of the constraint, critical chain tasks take precedence over all other activity. Finally, projects are planned and managed to ensure that resources are available when critical chain tasks must begin, prioritizing the critical chain over all other resources.

6.3. Earned value management

Earned value management (EVM), also known as earned value project management or earned value performance management (EVPM), is a project management approach used to objectively measure project performance and progress. Earned value management is a project management approach for assessing the performance and progress of a project. It has the capacity to incorporate the project management triangle's metrics of scope, time, and costs. Earned value management may give accurate predictions of project performance concerns in a single integrated system, which is a significant addition to project management. Early EVM analysis shown that its usage has a substantial influence on planning and control; similarly, applying the technique enhances both scope definition and total project performance analysis. The concepts of EVM have been found to be good indicators of project success in more recent research investigations. EVM's popularity has risen in recent years outside of government contracting, a sector in which its relevance is growing (e.g., recent new DFARS standards), in part because EVM can appear in contract disputes and assist justify them.

Essential features of any EVM implementation include:

- A project plan that identifies work to be accomplished
- A valuation of planned work, called planned value (PV) or budgeted cost of work scheduled (BCWS)
- pre-defined "earning rules" (also called metrics) to quantify the accomplishment of work, called earned value (EV) or budgeted cost of work performed (BCWP)
- Actual Cost which is also known as Actual Cost of Work Performed (ACWP)
- a plot of project cumulative costs vs time especially to show both early date and late date curves

Many additional capabilities are included in EVM implementations for big or complicated projects, such as indications and forecasts of cost performance (over budget or under budget) and schedule performance (behind schedule or ahead of schedule). The most fundamental need of an EVM system, on the other hand, is that it measures progress using PV and EV.

EVM example

Project A has been approved for a one-year period and a budget of X. It was also planned that the project would spend 50% of the approved budget in the first six months, with 50% of the work completed. If a project manager reports that he has spent 50% of the budget six months after the start of the project, one would assume that everything is going according to plan. In actuality, the information supplied is insufficient to reach such a decision. The project might

spend 50% of the budget while completing just 25% of the work, indicating that the project is not doing well; alternatively the project can spend 50% of the budget while completing 75% of the work, indicating that the project is performing better than expected. EVM is designed to deal with situations like this.

6.4. Iterative and incremental project management

In critical studies of project management, it has been highlighted that phased techniques are not well suited for large-scale and multi-company projects, as well as those with unclear, ambiguous, or rapidly changing needs, as well as those with high levels of risk, reliance, and rapidly changing technology. The cone of uncertainty explains some of this, since the planning done at the project's first phase is fraught with ambiguity. This is especially relevant because software development is frequently used to create a new or innovative product. A more exploratory or iterative and iterative approach is preferable for dealing with these challenges. Agile project management, dynamic systems development method, extreme project management, and Innovation Engineering are examples of iterative and incremental project management models that have evolved.

6.5. Phased management approach

The phased (or staged) approach divides and organizes the work into a number of discrete phases that must be accomplished, and is also known as "conventional" or "waterfall" management. It typically consists of five process areas, four phases plus control:

- initiation.
- planning and design.
- construction.
- monitoring and controlling.
- completion or closing.

(Typical development phases of an engineering project)

Many industries have different names for these project phases, and it's not unusual for the stages to be changed to fit the needs of the company. When working on a brick-and-mortar design and construction project, for example, pre-planning, conceptual design, schematic design, design development, construction drawings (or contract papers), and construction administration are common stages. While the phased approach works well for small, well-defined projects, it frequently leads to difficulty or failure for bigger, more complicated projects with more ambiguities, problems, and risk.

6.6. Project production management (PPM)

The application of operations management to the execution of capital projects is known as project production management. The Project production management framework is based on the idea of a project as a production system, in which a project converts inputs (raw materials, information, labor, plant, and machinery) into

outputs (goods and services). During the Industrial Revolution, the knowledge that underpins PPM was developed in the field of industrial engineering. During this period, industrial engineering developed and found use in a variety of fields, including military planning and logistics for both the First and Second World Wars, as well as manufacturing systems. Industrial engineering expanded into numerous scientific disciplines such as operations research, operations management, and queueing theory, among other areas of concentration, as a cohesive body of knowledge began to grow. The application of this set of knowledge to the execution of capital projects is known as Project Production Management (PPM). Project management, as defined by the Project Management Institute expressly excludes operations management from its body of knowledge, on the grounds that projects are one-time undertakings with a start and finish date, whereas operations relate to continuing or repeated tasks. However, by seeing a big capital project as a production system, such as that seen in construction, it is feasible to apply operations research, industrial engineering, and queueing theory theory and related technical frameworks to optimize, plan, control, and improve project performance.

7. ROLE OF BIM IN PROJECT MANAGEMENT

7.1. BIM vs. PMBOK Knowledge Areas

Since the nature and purpose of each item are similar, BIM capabilities on building projects match to PMBOK knowledge categories. As a result, BIM may be regarded as a useful and strong project management tool in the building sector. The first area of the PMBOK, which serves the same purpose as BIM, is integration management. BIM unifies the papers, plans, and activities of all project participants. BIM is also an object-based system that can categorize and break down the parts of a building into distinct categories, similar to how project scope management works. Another feature of BIM is its capacity to manage time and cost, which is referred to as 4D and 5D. This is comparable to the PMBOK standard's project cost and time management sections. Although constructability does not depict all hazards involved with a construction project, it is a useful tool in the construction process and helps to minimize construction risks. Clash detection is a quality control method in BIM that visually detects, changes, and analyzes soft and harsh conflicts. Human resource management views collaboration and team development in BIM to be a project management domain. BIM facilitates the professional connection between all parties involved in a building project, including project managers, designers, and engineers, by establishing effective and direct communication channels. Finally, quantity takeoffs generated by BIM would make procurement management practicable. Furthermore, changes in any item may readily be reflected in the cost, time, and effort required to obtain it. Despite the broad scope of project management, BIM may be viewed as a key and effective idea that corresponds to project management knowledge domains. Figure 2 depicts a model of PMBOK knowledge domains for building projects using BIM.

7.2. BIM Benefits and Advantages

Different sources of construction project management identify key advantages of using BIM as follows (Qian,2012)

- Enhanced project collaboration and control among stakeholders
- Improved productivity (less re-work, conflicts and changes)
- Better project quality and performance
- Faster project delivery
- Reduced wastage

- Reduced construction costs
- New revenue and business opportunities

BIM, as a centralized repository, allows everyone participating in building projects to have access to the same version of data, reducing the possibility of project managers' miscommunication (Alagarsamy, 2000). The major advantage of BIM in the pre-construction phase, according to Eastman et al. (2008), is concept, feasibility, and design analysis, which results in enhanced building performance and quality. In the design phase of a construction project, more accurate visualizations of a design, automatic low-level corrections when changes are needed, 2D drawings generation, earlier collaboration of multiple design parties, cost estimates extraction during the design stage, and energy efficiency and sustainability improvement are all advantages. In addition, BIM synchronizes design and construction planning, identifies design mistakes and omissions, uses design models as the foundation for manufactured components, and employs lean construction approaches during the building phase. In addition, adopting BIM in the post-construction phase would allow for improved facility administration and management.

7.3. Challenges with BIM

Personal opinions about the BIM have sparked some of the most heated debates about its implementation. According to a recent poll by Lahdou and Zetterman (2011), the outcome of a construction project would be unsatisfactory if project team members do not truly believe in the relevance of BIM and its benefits. In another case, according to a survey conducted by Qian (2012), the top rated areas of BIM for investment include software and hardware, as well as development. BIM workflow and processes, as well as BIM education, are all part of the internal collaborative BIM workflow. According to Brewer et al. (2012), the obstacles of utilizing BIM on construction projects may be divided into three categories: 1) technical challenges, which include disputes and concerns surrounding data sharing among team members, as well as BIM software issues; 2) skills and knowledge challenges, training issues, which mostly concern the training and development of project team members; 3) legal as well as procedural issues, such as a lack of a clear and legal definition for BIM professional duties; 4) Cost issues, which might make it difficult for construction companies to change and upgrade their present operations. systems to a BIM-based model.

8. EFFECTS OF BIM ON PROJECT MANAGEMENT

Some issues with the traditional management paradigm and technology can be resolved if the following guidelines are followed. It is possible to control the implementation process of construction entities using BIM, and some basic modifications will be made, such as distribution outlets, accumulation methods, and so on. BIM, as a result of these developments, creates new needs for project managers in terms of abilities, traits, and so on, and has a far-reaching influence on all elements of project management talent development as follows:

It is necessary for project managers to establish a BIM-centered information communication paradigm and to understand the benefits and conveniences of BIM-assisted project management. BIM is at the heart of modern project information communication (figure 1), and it underpins all delivery and communication. It is on this that information is built. In this case, project managers should build up a BIM-centered workflow. information

communication idea At the very least, the notion should have two levels: Firstly, To be effective, you must first understand the purposes of BIM; second, you must be able to distinguish between BIM and traditional 3D models. Meanwhile, in order to effectively use BIM, the project manager must have a thorough understanding of its merits. According to the standpoints of AGC, the effects of BIM on project management are as following: finding conflicts (such as the structure of pipeline, etc.), setting up visual model, judging the construction sit condition more reliably and protesting it with higher quality and less creative chances. What's more, it helps the managers to prepare more schemes, such as, different construction order, logistics organization, crane's location and costs, etc. It also helps non-professional members to see visual final products, so the number of reexamining and the costs of project guaranteeing are reduced . As a result, it is simple to see how BIM affects project management in many disciplines, and project managers should be aware of this.

Having a strong understanding of BIM tools and technology. Because BIM has become the center and foundation of information exchange, so the project managers should not only have a good command of BIM tools, but also fully understand some technologies related to project management. At the present, solutions of BIM are Autodesk's Revit, Bentley's MicroStation TriForma and Graphsoft's ArchiCAD, etc. These varied solutions are widely used in construction and they can be worked as a basis to guiding some managerial jobs and building models applied in management work, though they are mainly adopted to build construction, structure and MEP models and have some differences between models of the project management. In addition, some products can be used to build models that applied in the process of construction, etc. Some construction software, such as Autodesk's Naviswork and Garphisoft's Constructor, is more widely used in project management. Naviswork is used as a basic tool for all stakeholders involved in the project in the example above.

Understand fully some of the issues brought on by BIM. The use of BIM has altered project management processes and procedures, as well as the methods in which parties communicate. As a result, the project manager must be completely aware of the issues that BIM might generate. For example, how do you include BIM-related things in a contract? What should be done about the dangers it poses? How do you get rid of the expenses? And how do you deal with team structure changes? etc. On the one hand, because of these complex issues, To overcome these issues, some study is required; nevertheless, project managers should maintain a close eye on the situation. When confronted with these issues, have a clear head. Some hazards may arise if they fully utilize BIM. should cause worry

9. Discussion

Project Managers' education and Knowledge

As mutual connections are a key component of BIM, user characteristics have an impact on its efficacy. BIM users comprise all parties and professions engaged; as a result, team members' views, particularly project managers, should be taken into account as an important aspect. Project's experience level The success of BIM on a building project is directly related to the management. According to Qian (2012), The benefits and qualities of BIM are directly proportional to the amount of experience of the users. According to Hardin (2009), having an experienced BIM project manager on the project team is a critical component of project success. The project manager's BIM

knowledge expands BIM's capabilities beyond a software program to a holistic concept that integrates and organizes all parties and systems involved in the project. Thus, BIM expertise should not be seen as an excessive skill for building project managers; instead, having relevant BIM experience and expertise should be a criteria for admission to a program manager of a construction project.

Education is the foundation for professional development in the workplace. There are discrepancies in project management education between institutions and programs (Rokooei & Miralami, 2010; Rokooei, Azizi & Miralami, 2010). BIM education, like any other practical approach, begins as a theoretical concept. Along with the rising usage of BIM in business over the last decade, many institutions across the world have paid greater attention to it. They should pay more attention to BIM education and include it in their curricula. Universities in the United States, as pioneer educators, play a critical role in this respect. Construction engineering and management programs are the most common places to find BIM-related courses. The idea of BIM and the accompanying software trainings are taught in these courses. O'Brien and his colleagues (2003) developed a collaborative design course that made use of existing tools. The integrity of the system is an objective for this course. The process of design was highlighted. According to Peterson et al. (2010), professors at several colleges have attempted to provide cutting-edge courses geared at equipping students for professional collaboration and training development management principles based on the most recent technological advancements. They also demonstrated that using BIM-based project management tools to generate more realistic project-based class assignments is a good idea. Students can use this technique to apply several formal project management methods to real-world project management challenges. In a capstone course, Ghosh and Chasey (2013) utilized BIM as a concept in relevant construction management curriculum and used it as a new project management experience. Despite efforts to integrate BIM into construction management curricula, it appears that there is still a gap between BIM and project management education. By combining these two principles to offer BIM-oriented project management material, future project managers will have a solid foundation on which to build their theoretical and practical skills.

10. Conclusion

BIM is the new achievement when IT technology is used in construction field. The building has a significant impact. The article covers mainly the impact of BIM on project management information. And it will have a huge influence with the growth of BIM theory and technology. As a project manager it will continue to advance project management as long as theory and technology are very well known to the project manager. These characteristics have enabled BIM to play an important role as a new tool in project management. Obviously, a user should use BIM, like any other tool on a system, and a project manager is one of the finest people to fulfill this function. The effectiveness of BIM in the building process is closely related to the project manager as the core of decision making. BIM might, thus, instead of being a technical one for building projects, be regarded a management tool. This view is the outcome of a full BIM definition. What BIM does is not actually like what a software package does. Some further consideration is required, such as the function of the project manager

and the BIM in building projects Clear BIM concept comprehension and sufficient BIM expertise and experience. To that end, Building curriculum should include an efficient blend of BIM and project management elements available for the Students in their future professional careers pursuing project management roles.

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